

**AN ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR THE PREDICTION
OF INTERLAMINAR STRESSES IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES**

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ABSTRACT

Laminated composites exhibit multiple failure modes such as fiber breakage, fiber-matrix debonding within individual layers or delamination between layers. A practical design method that is both expedient and reliable for prediction of interlaminar stresses is needed for engineering analysis of delaminations. Most of the methods at hand do not provide a rapid predictive capability that is crucial to routine consideration of delamination related damages in composite materials. In order to allow efficient analysis of delamination effects on the residual properties of composite laminates, a new analytical laminated model has been developed. The model is based on an earlier theory, that is using a modified Donnell approach. This approach considers the classical engineering theory as a zeroth order approximation and adds to it successive higher order refinements. In this paper results are presented incorporating second order refinements in the formulation. The results from the model are compared with the corresponding finite element predictions for some sample cases. The correlations between the closed-form and finite element predictions show very good agreement.

KEYWORDS : Laminate; Delamination; Failure/Interlaminar; Two-Dimensional.

1. INTRODUCTION

Various methods are available for the analysis of composite laminates. These methods vary from analytical or closed form of the elasticity type to a wide variety of numerical techniques such as finite elements, boundary elements and finite differences.

Laminated composite structures exhibit multiple failure modes such as fiber breakage, fiber matrix debonding within individual layers, delamination between layers, cracks within the matrix or across different layers and fibers. Many of these failure modes are

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related to the so called interlaminar stresses. Effective prediction of interlaminar stresses is essential in designing structurally sound laminates, not prone to delamination.

Classical lamination theories (1,2) do not include the important effects of transverse shear and normal stresses at the ply interfaces since they rely on the Kirchhoff hypothesis. These effects, that are usually not significant for isotropic materials, may be of utmost importance in composite laminates because of their weakness in the transverse directions. Shear deformation was included by Mindlin (3) for isotropic elastic plates and then extended to laminated anisotropic plates by Yang, Norris and Stavsky (4). Pagano (5,6) developed exact solutions, within the framework of the linear theory of elasticity, and applied them to several boundary value problems. The results were compared with the analogous ones obtained from the classical lamination theory. Pipes and Pagano (7) treated the response of a finite width composite laminate subjected to a uniform extension in the longitudinal or axial direction, through the application of three dimensional classical elasticity, using finite difference approximations.

In a higher order theory by Whitney and Sun (8), where shear deformation is included, the inplane displacements were expressed as quadratic functions of the thickness coordinate and the transverse displacement having a linear variation across the laminate thickness. The governing equations were derived using Hamilton's principle. A new theory proposed by Pagano (9), was based on an extension of Reissner's variational principle to laminated bodies. In this formulation, because of the magnitudes of the numbers involved in the analysis, no more than six plies were considered.

In Reference (11), Rehfield and Valisetty have generalized the theory of Reference 10 for applications to laminates. In accomplishing this objective two assumptions were adopted, which provide the basis for a new theory. The first is that the transverse shear and normal strains can be estimated from the classical statically equivalent stresses. The second is that the influence of transverse normal stresses can be ignored in the constitutive relations. These two assumptions replace the Kirchhoff's assumption of the classical theory. The theory proposed by Armanios (12) was based on a modified Donnell approach. Herein the stresses obtained by the classical engineering theory are improved by adding a series of corrections. These corrections were determined by satisfying the stress equilibrium and compatibility conditions of two-dimensional elasticity. Other higher order theories (13,14), are based on cubic variations of the inplane displacements over the thickness of the laminate, whereas the transverse displacement is assumed constant.

The Pagano-Pipes (7) problem was analyzed by Wang and Crossman (15) using constant strain, triangular finite elements. To overcome the difficulty of computational storage, a limitation encountered by various authors, a programming procedure called Sky-line matrix storage scheme was adopted.

In summary, various methods exist to calculate interlaminar stresses and predict delaminations in fiber-reinforced composites. However, they often yield different results for the same problem, may require large amounts of computer storage and computer time

and may not therefore, be cost effective. Expedient and reliable predictions of interlaminar stresses during all stages of the design process are needed in order to effectively scrutinize delamination prone laminates.

A practical solution approach to this need, that is based on the governing equations of Reference (12) is presented here. It is effective and accurately predicts the interlaminar stresses in composite laminates. The accuracy of the model is assessed by comparing its predictions against corresponding results obtained for a sample case from a finite element model.

2. FORMULATION OF ELEMENT EQUATIONS

In this section, the development of the proposed model is described. The model is based on a modified Donnell approach where the stresses obtained from the classical engineering theory are improved by adding a series of corrections. These corrections are determined by satisfying the stress equilibrium and compatibility conditions of two dimensional elasticity. The analysis is restricted to orthotropic materials where the axes of the ply are chosen to coincide with the principal material directions, subjected to a plane stress state. The analysis can be easily extended to a plain strain situation by proper transformation of the elastic constants. Consider a laminate made of N perfectly bonded plies, each having a plane of material symmetry parallel to the plane of the laminate.

The overall equations of equilibrium for the k^{th} ply (Figure 1) in terms of force and moment resultants as derived by integrating the 2-D equilibrium equations are

$$\begin{aligned} N^k_{,x} + T_2^k - T_1^k &= 0 \\ Q^k_{,x} + P_2^k - p_1^k &= 0 \\ M^k_{,x} - Q^k + \frac{h^k}{2} (T_1^k + T_1^k) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $_{,x}$ denotes differentiation with respect to x . Superscript "k", which identifies the ply, is dropped in the subsequent equations for convenience.

FIGURE 1 : Generic Element with Resultant Forces, Moments and Surface Tractions.

For the general case, where the generic element is subjected to both interfacial transverse

normal and shear stresses, stress distributions are obtained by combining four different loading cases. This particular approach considers the classical engineering theory as a zeroth order approximation and adds to it successive higher order refinements. These refinements consist of functions in the thickness coordinate z , weighted by the derivatives of the interfacial stresses. In the general case where the ply is subjected to both interfacial transverse normal and shear stresses, the corresponding results are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{xx} &= \frac{N}{h} + 12 \frac{M}{h^3} z + \alpha \left[\frac{h}{12} \left(1 - \frac{12z^2}{h^2} \right) N_{,xx} + \frac{3z}{5h} \left(1 - \frac{20z^2}{3h^2} \right) M_{,xx} \right] \\
 &+ \frac{h^2 \alpha^2 \left[\left(\frac{27z}{1400h} - \frac{z^3}{5h^3} + \frac{2z^5}{5h^5} \right) M_{,xxxx} + \frac{h}{6} \left(\frac{7}{240} - \frac{z^2}{2h^2} + \frac{z^4}{h^4} \right) \right. \\
 &\left. N_{,xxxx} \right] + h^2 \frac{S_{33}}{S_{11}} \left[\frac{1}{24} \left(1 - \frac{12z^2}{h^2} \right) r_{,xx} - \frac{z}{h} \left(\frac{1}{40} - \frac{z^2}{6h^2} \right) Q_{,xxx} \right. \\
 &\left. - \left(\frac{11z}{1120h} - \frac{z^3}{12h^3} + \frac{z^5}{10h^5} \right) M_{,xxxx} - \frac{h}{8} \left(\frac{3}{80} - \frac{z^2}{2h^2} + \frac{z^4}{3h^4} \right) N_{,xxxx} \right] \\
 \sigma_{xz} &= \frac{Q}{h} - \frac{z}{h} N_{,x} + \frac{1}{2h} \left(1 - \frac{12z^2}{h^2} \right) M_{,x} + \alpha h \left[\left(\frac{1}{80} - \frac{3z^2}{10h^2} + \frac{z^4}{h^4} \right) \right. \\
 &\left. M_{,xxx} - \frac{z}{12} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) N_{,xxx} \right] \\
 \sigma_{zz} &= r - \frac{z}{h} Q_{,x} - \frac{h}{8} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) N_{,xx} - \frac{z}{2h} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) M_{,xx} \\
 &- \alpha h^2 \left[\left(\frac{z}{80h} - \frac{z^3}{10h^3} + \frac{z^5}{5h^5} \right) M_{,xxxx} + \frac{h}{12} \left(\frac{1}{16} - \frac{z^2}{2h^2} + \frac{z^4}{h^4} \right) N_{,xxxx} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where $\alpha = (S_{55} + 2S_{13}) / (2S_{11})$. If the underlined terms in equations (2) are neglected, that is, only one set of refinements is kept, the shear and transverse normal stress distributions consistent with the refined axial stress distribution are those of the classical theory.

Starting from the three constitutive and the three strain-displacement relations and following common integration procedures of elasticity theory, the displacement distributions are obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= \bar{u} - z \bar{w}_{,x} + \frac{z}{h} S_{55} Q + \frac{1}{2} (S_{55} + S_{13}) \left[\frac{h}{12} \left(1 - \frac{12z^2}{h^2} \right) N_{,x} \right. \\
 &+ \frac{z}{h} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) M_{,x} \left. + \frac{\alpha h^2}{12} (S_{55} + S_{13}) \left[h \left(\frac{7}{240} - \frac{z^2}{2h^2} + \frac{z^4}{h^4} \right) N_{,xxx} \right. \right. \\
 &+ \frac{6z}{5h} \left(\frac{1}{8} - \frac{z^2}{h^2} + \frac{2z^4}{h^4} \right) M_{,xxx} + \frac{h^2 S_{33}}{48} \left[2 \left(1 - \frac{12z^2}{h^2} \right) r_{,x} - 3h \left(\frac{3}{40} - \frac{z^2}{h^2} + \frac{2z^4}{3h^4} \right) N_{,xxx} \right. \\
 &\left. \left. - \frac{2z}{h} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) Q_{,xx} - \frac{z}{h} \left(\frac{7}{10} - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} + \frac{24z^4}{5h^4} \right) M_{,xxx} \right] \right] \\
 w &= \bar{w} + \frac{z}{h} S_{13} N - \frac{S_{13}}{2h} \left(1 - \frac{12z^2}{h^2} \right) M + \alpha h S_{13} \left\{ - \left(\frac{1}{80} - \frac{3z^2}{10h^2} + \frac{z^4}{h^4} \right) M_{,xx} \right. \\
 &+ \frac{h}{2} \left(\frac{z}{6h} - \frac{2z^3}{3h^3} \right) N_{,xx} + \frac{h^3}{2} \left[\frac{\alpha}{3} \left(\frac{7z}{240h} - \frac{z^3}{6h^3} + \frac{z^5}{5h^5} \right) - \frac{S_{33}}{6S_{13}} \left(\frac{z}{16h} - \frac{z^3}{6h^3} \right) \right. \\
 &+ \frac{z^5}{5h^5} \left. - \frac{S_{33}}{4\alpha S_{11}} \left(\frac{3z}{80h} - \frac{z^3}{6h^3} + \frac{z^5}{15h^5} \right) \right] N_{,xxxx} \left. + h S_{33} \left[\frac{z}{h} r - \frac{z}{8} \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{3h^2} \right) N_{,xx} \right. \right. \\
 &\left. \left. + \frac{1}{24} \left(1 - \frac{12z^2}{h^2} \right) Q_{,x} + \left(\frac{7}{480} - \frac{z^2}{4h^2} + \frac{z^4}{2h^4} \right) M_{,xx} \right] \right\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where \bar{u} and \bar{w} are the average axial and transverse displacements defined as

$$\bar{u} = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \frac{u}{h} dz \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{w} = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \frac{w}{h} dz \quad (4)$$

During this process, the constitutive equations are transformed into

$$N = \frac{h^3}{S_{11}} \left[\bar{u}_{,x} - S_{13} r + \frac{h}{12} S_{13} N_{,xx} + \frac{\alpha h^3}{360} S_{13} N_{,xxxx} \right]$$

$$M = \frac{h^3}{12S_{11}} \left[-\bar{w}_{,xx} + \frac{1}{h} (S_{55} + S_{13}) Q_{,x} + \frac{2\alpha}{5h} S_{11} M_{,xx} - \frac{S_{33}h}{60} Q_{,xxx} + \frac{h}{175} (\alpha^2 S_{11} - \frac{5}{6} S_{33}) M_{,xxxx} \right] \quad (5)$$

The underlined terms in these equations represent the contributions of the second set of refinements over the classical stress predictions.

3. METHOD OF SOLUTION

The above formulation is utilized here for the development of the appropriate solution for a specimen with two elements or group of plies, also known as sublaminate (Figure 2). Superscripts 1 and 2 that appear in subsequent equations, denote the upper and lower elements of the specimen. Continuity of axial and transverse displacements and reciprocity of interlaminar stresses is implied by the perfect interface assumption between the two sublaminate. These are

$$T_1^k = T_2^{k+1} T_2^{k+1}$$

$$P_1^k = P_2^{k+1} \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{u}_1^{-k} = \bar{u}_2^{-k+1}$$

$$\bar{w}_1^{-k} = \bar{w}_2^{-k+1}$$

FIGURE 2 : Specimen Configuration as Used in the Development of the Model

The equilibrium equations (1), the displacement distributions (3), the equations for the resultant force and moment in terms of average variables (5), the continuity requirements (6) and the appropriate surface boundary conditions make-up the governing system of

equations, whose solution is sought. The resulting system of ordinary differential equations is reduced further by expressing eight of the ten dependent variables in terms of the remaining two, which for example may be M^1 and M^2 . Such a reduction in the number of equations yields a 2x2 system of non-homogeneous ordinary differential equations in the form

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{bmatrix} A_{611} & A_{612} \\ A_{621} & A_{622} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M^1 \\ M^2 \end{Bmatrix},_{xxxxxx} + \begin{bmatrix} A_{411} & A_{412} \\ A_{421} & A_{422} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M^1 \\ M^2 \end{Bmatrix},_{xxxx} + \\ & \begin{bmatrix} A_{211} & A_{212} \\ A_{221} & A_{222} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M^1 \\ M^2 \end{Bmatrix},_{xx} + \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M^1 \\ M^2 \end{Bmatrix} \\ & = \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \end{Bmatrix} x^2 + \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \end{Bmatrix} x + \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \end{Bmatrix} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where A_{ijk} and α_i are constant coefficients having lengthy expressions involving material parameters and surface boundary conditions, respectively.

The general solution of each dependent variable of the system (for example, M^1 and M^2) consists of the sum of two parts : (i) a complementary solution forms the homogeneous part and (ii) a particular solution forms the non-homogeneous part. Since the equations are linear differential equations with constant coefficients, the complementary solution for each dependent variable consists of a series of terms in the general form

$$M_c = F e^{\lambda x} \tag{8}$$

where F is a vector. It contains constants that represent the eigenvalues of the system of equations derived from either equation of the homogeneous system.

After the assumed solution is substituted in the homogeneous system of equations, values for λ are found by setting the determinant of the coefficients (Equation 9) equal to zero. Algebraic expressions for the expansion of the determinant are not written here for the sake of brevity. In a condensed form the determinant (characteristic equation) of the system is

$$E_1 S^{10} + E_2 S^8 + E_3 S^6 + E_4 S^4 + E_5 S^2 + E_6 = 0 \tag{9}$$

where E 's are constant coefficients. The roots of the polynomial equation (9) furnish the values of λ and are calculated through a standard numerical method (15).

The second part of the general solution is the particular solution. A polynomial of the second degree is assumed to be the desired particular solution that satisfies the non-homogeneous system of differential equations. This assumed solution is of the form

$$M_p = \begin{Bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \end{Bmatrix} x^2 + \begin{Bmatrix} \beta_3 \\ \beta_4 \end{Bmatrix} x + \begin{Bmatrix} \beta_5 \\ \beta_6 \end{Bmatrix} \tag{10}$$

where β 's are constant coefficients which are determined by substituting the above solution in the system of equations and then by balancing the terms of either side.

Combining equations (8) and (10) the general solution becomes

$$M = M_c + M_p \quad (11)$$

This is the general solution for the dependant variables, M^1 and M^2 , of the system of ordinary differential equations when the second set of refinements is included.

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The proposed analytical model has been validated by applying it to a flat laminate composed of two distinct elements, as shown in Figure 3. Each element is treated as a homogeneous orthotropic region under a plane stress condition. The specimen is fixed at one end and is subjected to uniform axial extension at the free end. Plywise edge boundary conditions are satisfied in an overall sense, by prescribing the following parameters :

$$\begin{aligned} &N \text{ or } \bar{u} \\ &Q \text{ or } \bar{w} \\ &\text{and } M \text{ or } \bar{\phi} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\phi}$ represents a suitable rotation-related condition. The modeling of boundary conditions in the classical theory is straightforward since the displacement varies linearly through the entire laminate thickness. The situation is more complex here. Section warping does not permit unique, fully satisfactory definition of a fixed edge. Since the purpose of this work is not to investigate section warping effects but rather to show the effectiveness of the proposed model in predicting interlaminar stresses, only one rotation related condition is used. This is the average or mean rotation of the laminate cross-section. It is defined as

$$\bar{\phi} = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} (u, z) dz = \frac{1}{h} \left[u(x, \frac{h}{2}) - u(x, -\frac{h}{2}) \right] \quad (13)$$

Numerical results have been obtained by using both the improved model, that includes second order refinements (Refined I, II) and also the simpler model that accounts for the first order refinements only (Simplified). For the sample case chosen here, attention is focused on the fixed boundary region where high stress gradients are expected. The specimen selected in the present analysis is characterized by the following data :

Top Layer: $E_{11} = 38.6 \text{ GPa}$ $E_{33} = 8.27 \text{ GPa}$ $\nu_{21} = 0.26$ $G_{12} = 4.14 \text{ GPa}$	Bottom Layer : $E_{11} = 138.0 \text{ GPa}$ $E_{33} = 8.96 \text{ GPa}$ $\nu_{21} = 0.3$ $G_{13} = 7.1 \text{ GPa}$
Applied axial strain $\epsilon_{xx} = 500$ microstrains.	Lenght/Thickness Ratio = 5

FIGURE 3 : Laminate Used in the Numerical Results.

In order to verify the accuracy of the present formulation, the problem is solved using a finite element code developed in house. The proposed model solution, labelled "Refined I" and "Refined II", incorporates a second set of refinements. This second set of refinements is implemented by incorporating the underlined terms shown in equations (2), (3) and (5). The Refined I model uses the first six roots predicted by equation (9), whereas Refined II uses only the first four. The "Simplified" model represents the solution if the underlined terms are neglected. This model predicts only four roots.

The variation of the transverse normal stress, σ_{zz} , and the transverse shear stress, σ_{xz} , along the interface of the two sublaminate is shown in Figures (4a) and (4b), respectively. From Figure (4a) the Refined I and II models give close predictions at the fixed end, but only Refined I converges to the finite element results within a very short distance from the boundary. Results from the Simplified model completely overestimate predictions from the other models. In Figure (4b) the peak value predicted by the Refined II model is closer to that of the finite element model. On the other hand results from the Refined I model converge much faster to the finite element ones.

Stress distributions at the midplane of the top sublaminate are shown in Figures (5a) and (5b). Excellent agreement between the results of the Refined I and finite element model is observed, Figure (5a), for the transverse normal stress. At the fixed boundary, different values are predicted by each model for the transverse shear stress. For a very small distance away from the fixed support the Refined I predictions show good correlation. Results from the Simplified model, as shown earlier, overestimate the stress. Comparative results, in Figures (4a) and (5b), clearly show the importance of a second order refinement (underlined terms) in capturing the true response in regions of high stress gradients.

Distributions for the transverse normal and shear stress at the midplane of the bottom sublaminate are shown in Figures (6a) and (6b), respectively. For the transverse normal stress, both Refined I and II models predict similar values that are slightly overestimated by the finite element ones. Results from the Refined I and finite element models show better correlation. For the transverse shear stress, Figure (6b), results from the Refined II and finite element models correlate better at the fixed boundary. However away from the fixed boundary Refined I shows better agreement.

Overall, excellent agreement is obtained for the transverse normal stress between the proposed model (Refined I) and the finite element results. Reasonable agreement is obtained for the transverse shear stress. The difference observed at the laminate's interface for the transverse shear stress may be attributed to the fact that the finite

element model does not ensure interlaminar continuity between plies or layers of different elastic constants.

FIGURE 4 : Transverse Stress Distributions at Laminate Interface

FIGURE 5 : Transverse Stress Distributions at Midplane of Top Layer.

FIGURE 6 : Transverse Stress Distributions at Midplane of Bottom Layer.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an analytical laminated field model has been presented. It is reliable and its application is simple enough for a practical design environment. This model is expected to serve as an important tool for the parametric design approach, where a large number of possible configurations are to be evaluated expediently and with a reasonable level of accuracy. The validity of the model is not limited to any particular laminate system. It is of a generic nature and can be used for studying the interlaminar stresses in MMC, PMC or CMC laminates. As such, the model can concurrently be used for several composite systems. The results from the proposed models were compared with the corresponding finite element predictions for a sample case. Comparative results show good agreement.

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